

Kinetics of thermal dehydration and decomposition of hydrated chlorides of some 3d transition metals (Mn-Cu series). Part-V. Dehydration and decomposition of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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Unlike dehydration of the dihydrate chlorides of other metal ions of Mn-Cu series, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dehydrates in one step without pre-melting. The anhydrous salt decomposes in air in three steps yielding CuO as final product. The kinetics of dehydration studied by non-isothermal method show that while in static air progress of reaction interface (R3) fits the data best, in flowing nitrogen random nucleation within bulk material (F1) appears to be the best fit model. However, the rate of first step of decomposition follows nucleation and growth (A3) with an E value of $106.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

It has been observed that tetrahydrated chlorides¹ of Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} and hexahydrated chlorides^{1,2} of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} dehydrate in three steps, losing 2, 1, 1 and 4, 1, 1 moles of H_2O respectively. However, it has been reported³ that $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dehydrates in single step without pre-melting. This suggests that the bonding of H_2O with metal ion in $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is different from its preceding hydrated metal chlorides of the Mn-Cu series.

Only a very few studies with limited objectives have been carried out on the dehydration and decomposition of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. For example, Tanaka and Koga³ have studied kinetics of dehydration of the salt and its admixture with KCl ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{KCl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in connection with their main investigation on kinetic compensation effect. Similarly, Ball and Coultard⁴ have used $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as part of the overall study on dehydration and decomposition characteristics of a number of halides and basic halides of copper. Mohamed

and Halawy⁵ have studied the kinetics of dehydration decomposition behavior of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ under flowing N_2 environment, but without stating anything about physical picture of the mechanism. In this paper an attempt has been made to make more detailed investigation on the kinetics of dehydration and decomposition of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ using non-isothermal method.

Results and discussion

Fig.1 illustrates some typical TG/DTA traces of the dehydration of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air and in flowing N_2 environments. It also illustrates the decomposition behavior of the salt in air at $4^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. It can be seen that the salt completely dehydrates in single step at temperature about $92\text{--}128^\circ\text{C}$ depending upon heating rate. The anhydrous salt remains stable at least up to 350°C and then decomposes in three steps before reaching the final plateau corresponding

Table 1. TG/DTA data of the dehydration of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air and flowing nitrogen atmosphere

Heating rate	Dehydration in static air			Dehydration in flowing nitrogen		
	Temperature	DTA peak	Moles of H_2O	Temp.	DTA peak	Moles of H_2O
	range	temp.	lost	range	temp.	lost
$^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$	$(T_i - T_c)^*$, $^\circ\text{C}$	($^\circ\text{C}$)	(% mass loss)	$(T_i - T_c)^*$, $^\circ\text{C}$	$^\circ\text{C}$	(% mass loss)
2	68.5–102	93	1.94 (20.5)	64.6–101	90	1.90 (20.1)
4	70–117	102	1.88 (19.8)	67.5–111	96.5	1.95 (20.6)
6	71–125	107	2.00 (21.1)	60.0–125	104	1.98 (20.9)
8	65–140	116	1.99 (21.0)	61.0–132.5	107	1.97 (20.8)
10	89–160	128	2.00 (21.1)	–	–	–

* T_i and T_c represent temperature of inception and temperature of completion of DTA peak respectively.

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Table 2. TG/DTA of the decomposition of CuCl_2 in static air

Heating rate °C/min	First stage of decomposition			Second stage of decomposition			Third stage of decomposition	
	Approx. temp. range	DTA peak temp.	% Mass loss	Approx. temp. range	DTA peak temp.	% Mass loss	Temp. range	% Mass loss at the third break
5	430-458	440	16.0	458-500	467, 485	5.6	500-660	22.0
8	420-474	455	17.0	474-507	478, 485	5.0	507-680	31.1
10	435-480	448	15.0	480-590	473	5.5	590-720	27.2

Table 3. Kinetic models and Arrhenius parameters derived from α -time data at different temperatures using the isoconversion method for the dehydration and decomposition of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Nature of reaction step	Average θ range (min)	α range	Temperature range (K)	Kinetic model (code)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)	Arrhenius parameters		
						E (kJ mol^{-1})	$\log A$ (min)	R^2
Dehydration in static air	(1.634-8.097) $\times 10^{10}$	0.1-0.90	368-388	R3	0.9985	71.2	8.91	1.0
Dehydration in N_2 atoms	(2.75-25.90) $\times 10^{10}$	0.05-0.90	363-378	R3	0.9978	66.4	8.47	1.0
-	-	0.1-0.95	-	F1	0.9957	66.5	9.13	1.0
Decomposition in air (1st step)	(0.687-11.28) $\times 10^8$	0.05-0.90	680-720	A2	0.9945	106.1	7.06	1.0
-	-	-	-	A3	0.9965	106.2	6.90	1.0

to the formation of CuO at temperature above 650°C . The temperature and mass loss data for different steps of dehydration and decomposition are given in Tables 1 and 2. From X-ray diffraction studies at different temperatures between 350 – 500°C it has been established that decomposition takes place through the intermediate formation of oxychloride ($\text{CuO} \cdot \text{CuCl}_2$). Using the calibration curve of the instrument (see Fig. 1, Ref. 1) the heats of dehydration and decomposition have been estimated from the area under the corresponding DTA peaks at $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The values are 128.8 and 65.5 kJ mol^{-1} respectively.

Kinetics of dehydration :

The kinetics of dehydration of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in static air have been studied using the isoconversion method as followed in one of the preceding papers. From the slope values of the linear plots of $\log(\text{heating rate})$ vs $1/T$ where T is the temperature in K, the E values calculated vary from 91.0 kJ mol^{-1} at $\alpha = 0.1$ to 54.6 kJ mol^{-1} at $\alpha = 0.9$ with a mean value of 71.0 kJ mol^{-1} . α represents fractional dehydration/conversion. Using the mean E value the reduced time (θ) is calculated for different values of α at the three heating rates employed. The mean θ values are then used to calculate isothermal time t for each corresponding value of α . The $\alpha - t$ data at three temperatures within the reaction regime fit the progress of the reactant-product interface with spherical symmetry (R3) model best (see Table 3).

Similarly, the slopes of the linear isoconversion plots for dehydration under flowing N_2 at 4° , 6° and $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$

Fig. 1. Typical examples of simultaneous TG/DTA of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in air and in flowing nitrogen environment. The hatched area under the DTA peak at $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in air is used for the estimation of heat of dehydration.

yield the E values varying from 83.7 ($\alpha = 0.05$) to 52.8 kJ mol^{-1} ($\alpha = 0.95$) with a mean value of 66.4 kJ mol^{-1} . Following the same procedure as above it has been observed that $\alpha - t$ data fit both F1 and R3 models almost equally well as shown in Table 3. This is possible, since rapid diffusion of water vapor facilitated by the flowing N_2 renders random nucleation within the entire volume of the bulk solid a slow process. Similar phenomenon was also observed⁶ in the case of dehydration of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. How-

ever, considering the little higher value of correlation coefficient (R^2), R3 is believed to be the likely mechanism (Table 3).

Decomposition of anhydrous salt :

It has been shown from TG curve that anhydrous CuCl_2 decomposes in three steps to CuO . However, except the first step, mechanism of the other two steps are not clear because of the possible occurrence of volatilization of anhydrous CuCl or CuCl_2 at higher temperature. Therefore, kinetics of decomposition has been studied for the first step (360–480°C) which represents the following reaction.

For this study, however, higher heating rates were used as in Table 2. The plot of fractional mass loss (α) vs temperature in Kelvin and isoconversion plots at different values of α are found to be linear and almost parallel to each other. The E values obtained from the slopes of these plots are nearly similar giving the mean value of $106.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Following the same procedure as above isothermal time t for different values of α at 680, 700 and 720 K are calculated. The data are found to fit nucleation and growth controlled models (A2 and A3) equally well. However, A3 is possibly more appropriate because of higher R^2 value (Table 3).

Experimental

About 5 g of freshly procured 'Pro-Analyse' grade

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck, India) was ground in an agate mortar until the entire powder passes through $150 \mu\text{m}$ sieve. The ground material was transferred into a well-capped sample bottle and stored in a desiccator over silica gel.

Simultaneous TG/DTA experiments were carried out in a Shimadzu Thermal Analyzer (model DT-40, Japan) according to the procedure described in the first part of this series¹. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the compound heated at different temperatures were obtained by using CuK_α radiation in a Phillips diffractometer fitted with a high temperature goniometer (temperature accuracy $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$).

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